

An Investigative Study on Information-Searching Skills of Undergraduate Students from a Non-State Degree Awarding Institution

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Abstract

The ability to locate, evaluate, and use information effectively is a core competency for academic success and lifelong learning. This study examines the information-searching skills of first-year undergraduate students at Horizon Campus, a non-state degree-awarding institution in Sri Lanka. It aims to assess students' existing library and information literacy (IL) skills, identify gaps in their information-searching behavior, and propose strategies to strengthen their learning support. Understanding these competencies is crucial for academic libraries seeking to develop evidence-based IL programs aligned with institutional needs. A quantitative, descriptive survey design was employed, and data were collected through an online questionnaire distributed to a population of 190 first-year students from diverse educational backgrounds. A total of 94 valid responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics to examine patterns of library use, preferred information sources, and challenges encountered in the search process. Among the respondents (n=94), most students are motivated to use the library mainly by lecturers (49%), followed by librarians (29%), while only a few are self-motivated. Books remain the most preferred information source (72%), with limited use of journals and other scholarly materials. A majority of students (82%) rely on both print and electronic formats, and most access information primarily through title and subject research. These results highlight students' limited independent search skills and the need for targeted support. The study recommends enhancing information literacy training by integrating it into the curriculum and conducting regular workshops to improve search and evaluation skills. Strengthening collaboration between lecturers and librarians can further promote effective and independent use of library resources.

Keywords: *Information Literacy, Information Searching, Library Instruction, Undergraduate Students, Academic Libraries*